

Facile synthesis of 1,3,4-thiadiazole appended to coumarins as antimicrobial agents

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Abstract : A new series of *N*-[4-acetyl-4,5-dihydro-5-methyl-5-(6,7-disubstituted-coumarin-3'-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl]-acetamide (**4a-f**) were synthesized from semicarbazones **3a-f** and acetic anhydride. The structure of all the synthesized compounds was confirmed by analytical and spectral (IR, ¹H, ¹³C NMR and MS) data. All the compounds were screened for their pharmacological parameters for bioavailability using Osiris property explorer. Amongst the title compounds **4a**, **4d** and **4e** have shown excellent drug likeliness and drug score values and did not exhibit any drug toxicity viz. mutagenicity, tumorigenicity, reproductive effect and irritant nature. Eventually these compounds are biologically safe for intake.

Keywords : Coumarin, 1,3,4-thiadiazole, drug score, MIC.

Introduction

The study of biological activities of coumarin derivatives has been the aim of many workers since from two decades¹⁻⁴ as most of these compounds were proved to be active as antitumor^{5,6}, antibacterial^{7,8}, antifungal⁹⁻¹¹, anticoagulant¹² and anti-inflammatory¹³. Some of the coumarin derivatives were reported to be used as additives in food and cosmetics¹⁴. The cyclization of suitable linear compounds like thiosemicarbazones or compounds with the basic skeleton S-C-N-N-C-S- is one of the most popular methods for preparing heterocyclic compounds¹⁵. 2,4-Disubstituted-semicarbazones have been proposed as dipeptide isosteres and are a new class of urea peptide mimetics. The possible pharmacological

properties of thiosemicarbazone derivatives make it attractive to study the reactivity of these compounds. 1,3,4-Thiadiazole derivatives exhibit various biological activities due to the presence of the -N=C-S moiety¹⁶. They are known to exhibit diverse biological properties like antimicrobial, antitubercular, antiinflammatory and anti-convulsant¹⁷⁻²². Based on these findings, we herein describe the synthesis of coumarin derivatised with 1,3,4-thiadiazole with the aim of obtaining more potent pharmacologically active compounds. The present investigation is mainly focused on the synthesis of 1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatised with coumarin **4a-f** from thiosemicarbazone of 3-acetyl coumarin **3a-f** using acetic anhydride as an efficient cyclising agent in a one-pot reaction. The method

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

applied for the preparation of title compounds is simple, efficient with higher yields.

Results and discussion

3'-Acetylcoumarin (**1a-f**) when reacted with thiosemicarbazide, 1-(1-(coumarin-3'-yl)-ethylidene)-thiosemicarbazone (**3a-f**) was obtained. The title compound **4a-f** was then formed by cyclization of the compound **3a-f** on heating with acetic anhydride. The structure of the title compounds was confirmed by spectral (IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR, Mass) and elemental analysis. All the title compounds **4a-f** have exhibited 3 sharp IR stretching bands due to the presence of lactone and two amide carbonyls. The lactone carbonyl of coumarin ring appeared around 1722 to 1736 cm^{-1} and the amide carbonyls appeared around 1610 – 1660 cm^{-1} . All these compounds **4a-f** have also exhibited the amide NH stretching band around 3380 – 3420 cm^{-1} . The ^1H NMR spectra of all the final products have shown 3 singlets each for three protons due to three methyl groups in the range δ 2.14–2.60 ppm viz. the one attached to the 1,3,4-thiadiazole

ring (at C_5 carbon) and the two attached to the amide carbonyl group. The protons of the coumarin appeared in the aromatic region. The NH of the amide group appeared as broad singlet (D_2O exchanged) in the range δ 8.00–8.20 ppm in all the final products. The ^{13}C NMR spectra of all these compounds showed the number of signals which are in consistent with the number of carbons in the molecule. So also, in the electron impact studies, all the compounds have exhibited molecular ion peaks at their respective m/z .

Pharmacological parameters study :

Using Osiris property explorer we have attempted to analyze the compounds **4a-f** for their drug likeliness by considering the values of $c \log P$, toxicity and drug score. The $c \log P$ is an important physicochemical property indicating the lipophilicity and the ability of molecule to cross the various biological membranes. According to Lipinski's rule of five the $c \log P$ value below 5 is feasible for a novel molecule to be a future drug. All the newly synthesized compounds **4a-f** showed remarkable values for $c \log P$ (Table 1). Among all the compounds the mol-

Table 1. Pharmacological parameters for bioavailability of the compounds **4a-f**

Entry	Mtg	Tmg	Irr	Re	$c \log P$	Solubility	Mol wt.	Drug likeliness	Drug score
4a	-	-	-	+	2.55	-4.46	345	6.93	0.44
4b	+	-	-	-	3.25	-5.30	423	4.80	0.45
4c	-	-	-	-	3.94	-6.13	501	4.47	0.40
4d	-	-	-	-	3.16	-5.20	379	6.94	0.61
4e	-	-	-	-	3.77	-5.94	413	6.49	0.49
4f	+	-	-	-	3.73	-6.07	395	4.45	0.40

- No effect, + Mild.

Mtg - Mutagenic effect, Tmg - Tumorigenic effect, Irr - Irritant nature,

Re - Reproductive effect.

ecule **4c** which has two bromine atoms on the coumarin ring showed favorable value for $c \log P$, as compared to the other compounds. A marginal lipophilicity within the range of 4.00–5.00 was observed for these compounds. The molecular weight property of the compound is related to its *in vivo* administration. Some of the compounds like **4b**, **4e** and **4c** have shown the molecular weight within the acceptable range that is 400–500. Interestingly, the compounds also presented a better drug likeliness values. Among all the compounds **4a**, **4d** and **4e** showed a very good drug likeliness values and even the molecules **4b**, **4c** and **4f** also have shown good drug likeliness but less compared to the remaining compounds. Overall, the compounds **4d** and **4e** showed a good drug score, calculated by combining all the parameters. A molecule may be used as the drug only if its toxicity is very less. Hence, drug toxicity is a factor of great importance for a potential commercial drug. Since a significant number of drugs are disapproved in chemical trials based on their high toxicity profile. The toxicity of the title compounds is calculated in terms of mutagenicity, tumorigenic, reproductive effect and irritant. The compounds **4a**, **4b** and **4f** have shown very mild reproductive and mutagenic effect, where as none of the compounds showed tumorigenicity and irritant effect. Eventually, these compounds can be said to be biologically safe for intake. The results of antimicrobial studies are almost in agreement with the drug likeliness and drug score parameters reported by Osiris property explorer.

In vitro antibacterial and antifungal activity :

In the present study, the antimicrobial activities of the newly synthesized compounds were evaluated against four micro organisms viz. *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus cereus* for antibacterial and *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger* for antifungal analyses. The comparative activities of the newly synthesized compounds **4a-f** and the control antibiotics chloramphenicol and ketoconazole on bacterial and fungal strains respectively were summarized in Table 2. The compounds **4e** (two *chloro* substituents) exhibited the growth inhibition almost equal to the standard drug against both the bacterial strains (MIC value 1.95, 6.50 mg/ml). The compound **4d** (one *chloro* substituent) showed good activity against *B. cereus* only (6.50 mg/ml). Even in case of the antifungal activity assay the compound **4a** (MIC 1.50 and 3.25 mg/ml) and **4e** (1.50 mg/

Table 2. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of the compounds **4a-f** and standard drugs expressed as (mg/mL)

Entry	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
4a	3.25	12.5	1.50	3.25
4b	12.5	12.5	6.50	12.5
4c	15.6	6.50	12.5	6.50
4d	6.50	6.50	3.25	3.25
4e	1.95	6.50	1.50	1.50
4f	62.5	12.5	31.5	6.25
Control 1	1.95	6.50	–	–
Control 2	–	–	0.97	1.50

Control 1 – Chloramphenicol, Control 2 – Ketoconazole.

ml each) have shown the remarkable activity against both *C. albicans* and the *A. niger*. The other compounds have shown good to moderate activity against both the bacterial and fungal strains. These results are in compatible with the Osiris property explorer values, where these compounds have higher drug score.

Conclusion :

Novel series of 1,3,4-thiadiazoles derivatised with coumarin **4a-f** were synthesized by an easy work-up. The advantage of the present method is one-pot cyclisation with excellent yield. The compounds were tested for their toxicity and drug score was evaluated by property prediction explorer. The antimicrobial activities indicated that the compounds **4a** and **4e** have activity almost equal to the standard drugs.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on Nicolet Impact 410FT IR spectrophotometer using KBr films or nujol. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR were recorded on Bruker 300-MHz FT NMR spectrometer in CDCl_3 and $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ with TMS as an internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on a GCMS-SC/AD/17-004 and elemental analysis was carried out using Heraeus CHN rapid analyzer. TLC was performed on silica gel coated plates for monitoring the reactions.

N-(4-Acetyl-4,5-dihydro-5-methyl-5-(6,7-substituted-2-oxo-2H-chromen-3-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-acetamide (**4a-f**) :

A mixture of **3a** (1 g, 3.8 mmol) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) was heated at 70–80 °C for 4 h. The solution was

cooled and poured into water. The solid formed was filtered washed with water and recrystallized from absolute ethanol to form **4a**. Similarly, the compounds **4b-f** were prepared.

N-(4-Acetyl-4,5-dihydro-5-methyl-5-(coumarin-3-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-acetamide (**4a**) :

Yield 85%, m.p. 248–249 °C; IR (film) : 2921 (N-H), 1722 (C=O), 1618 (C=N), 1476 (C-S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 2.05 (3H, s, 5'-Me), 2.16 (3H, s, 4'-COCH₃), 2.20 (3H, s, C₂-N-COCH₃), 7.70 (1H, s, C₄ Ar-H), 7.20–7.67 (5H, m, Ph), 8.05 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 22 (Me of NHCOCH₃), 23 (Me of NCOCH₃), 25 (C₅-Me), 49.00, 121.50, 122.30, 128.40, 125.50, 126.80, 127.90, 139.80, 144.10, 150.20, 162.00, 168.30, 171.60; MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z 345 (M⁺), 330 (15), 303 (27), 288 (15), 270 (18), 246 (36), 228 (22), 218 (10), 207 (17), 188 (15), 173 (13), 158 (15), 144 (14), 127 (17), 115 (12), 89 (26), 75 (14), 57 (18), 43 (14) (Found : C, 54.30; H, 3.88; N, 12.70. C₁₅H₁₂N₃O₄S requires : C, 54.37; H, 3.95; N, 12.68%).

N-(4-Acetyl-4,5-dihydro-5-methyl-5-(6-bromocoumarin-3-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-acetamide (**4b**) :

Yield 83%, m.p. 210–212 °C; IR (film) : 2932 (N-H), 1730 (C=O), 1610 (C=N), 1482 (C-S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 2.06 (3H, s, 5'-Me), 2.14 (3H, s, 4'-COCH₃), 2.24 (3H, s, C₂-N-COCH₃), 7.56–7.84 (4H, m, Ph), 8.05 (1H, s, N-H); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 22.00 (Me of NHCOCH₃), 23.0 (Me of NCOCH₃), 25.40 (C₅-Me), 49.00, 119.80, 124.50, 127.90, 130.30, 131.30, 139.80, 144, 162, 168.30, 171.60; MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z 423 (M⁺), 396 (27), 378 (18), 342 (36), 314 (28), 290 (24), 264 (26), 248 (16), 223 (25), 201 (22), 189 (12), 172 (17), 158 (14), 132 (26), 117 (15) (Found : C, 43.80; H, 2.82; N, 10.20. C₁₅H₁₁N₃BrO₄S requires : C, 43.92; H, 2.95; N, 10.24%).

N-(4-Acetyl-4,5-dihydro-5-methyl-5-(6,7-dibromocoumarin-3-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-acetamide (**4c**) :

Yield 78%, m.p. 157–159 °C; IR (film) : 2942 (N-H), 1736 (C=O), 1612 (C=N), 1478 (C-S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 2.12 (3H, s, 5'-Me), 2.20 (3H, s, 4'-COCH₃), 2.25 (3H, s, C₂-N-COCH₃), 7.34–

7.55 (3H, m, Ph), 8.1 (1H, s, N-H); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 19.00 (Me of NHCOCH₃), 23.05 (Me of NCOCH₃), 25.80 (C₅-Me), 48.80, 122.70, 123.50, 125.60, 127, 127.90, 132.50, 139.80, 144, 151.40, 162, 168.30, 171.60; MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z 501 (M⁺), 478 (23), 445 (33), 418 (27), 402 (16), 353 (49), 317 (36), 298 (19), 263 (35), 248 (15) (Found : C, 36.80; H, 2.15; N, 8.45. C₁₅H₁₀N₃Br₂O₄S requires : C, 36.83; H, 2.27; N, 8.59%).

N-(4-Acetyl-4,5-dihydro-5-methyl-5-(6-chlorocoumarin-3-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-acetamide (**4d**) :

Yield 82%, m.p. 174–175 °C; IR (film) : 2938 (N-H), 1728 (C=O), 1612 (C=N), 1480 (C-S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 2.15 (3H, s, 5'-Me), 2.20 (3H, s, 4'-COCH₃), 2.30 (3H, t, C₂-N-COCH₃), 7.10–7.75 (4H, m, Ph), 7.95 (1H, s, N-H); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 21.00 (Me of NHCOCH₃), 23.20 (Me of NCOCH₃), 24.80 (C₅-Me), 49.20, 122.90, 123, 126, 127, 128.50, 131, 139.80, 144, 162, 168.30, 171.60; MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z 379 (M⁺), 348 (31), 323 (25), 305 (18), 286 (19), 253 (33), 227 (26), 214 (13), 205 (9), 185 (20), 170 (15), 152 (18), 134 (18), 113 (21), 99 (24), 85 (14) (Found : C, 49.10; H, 3.22; N, 11.40. C₁₅H₁₁N₃ClO₄S requires : C, 49.25; H, 3.31; N, 11.49%).

N-(4-Acetyl-4,5-dihydro-5-methyl-5-(6,7-dichlorocoumarin-3-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-acetamide (**4e**) :

Yield 92%, m.p. 193–195 °C; IR (film) : 2935 (N-H), 1730 (C=O), 1614 (C=N), 1485 (C-S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 2.09 (3H, s, 5'-Me), 2.19 (3H, s, 4'-COCH₃), 2.32 (3H, t, C₂-N-COCH₃), 7.62–8.10 (3H, m, Ph), 8.16 (1H, s, N-H); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 22.40 (Me of NHCOCH₃), 23.10 (Me of NCOCH₃), 25.30 (C₅-Me), 48.8, 121.80, 123.70, 127, 128.30, 130, 133, 139.60, 144, 149, 162, 168.80, 171; MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z 413 (M⁺), 398 (15), 373 (25), 342 (31), 315 (27), 293 (22), 272 (21), 253 (19), 237 (16), 212 (25), 201 (11), 187 (14), 175 (12) (Found : C, 44.90; H, 2.62; N, 10.43. C₁₅H₁₀N₃Cl₂O₄S requires : C, 45.01; H, 2.77; N, 10.5%).

N-(4-Acetyl-4,5-dihydro-5-methyl-5-(benzo[g]coumarin-3-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-acetamide (**4f**) :

Yield 74%, m.p. 155–157 °C; IR (film) : 2946 (N-

H), 1734 (C=O), 1610 (C=N), 1495 (C-S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 2.05 (3H, s, 5'-Me), 2.14 (3H, s, 4'-COCH₃), 2.35 (3H, s, C₂-N-COCH₃), 7.2–7.7 (6H, m, Ph), 7.80 (1H, s, C₄ Ar), 8.15 (1H, s, N-H); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 22 (Me of NHCOCH₃), 23 (Me of NCOCH₃), 25.50 (C₅-Me), 117.40, 177.80, 122.30, 123.60, 126.80, 127.90, 128.50, 128.80, 130, 131.90, 139.80, 144, 168.30, 171.60; MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z 395 (M^+), 378 (17), 362 (16), 348 (14), 332 (16), 307 (25), 298 (9), 283 (15), 262 (21), 248 (14), 233 (15), 217 (16), 203 (14) (Found : C, 59.65; H, 3.80; N, 10.90. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires : C, 59.83; H, 3.96; N, 11.02%).

Antimicrobial assay :

Antimicrobial activities of the newly synthesized compounds were evaluated using microbroth dilution method²³. Micro-organisms selected for the assay were *E. coli*, *B. cereus* for antibacterial and *C. albicans*, *A. niger* for antifungal studies. Microbroth dilution susceptibility assay was used for antimicrobial evaluation of the compounds. Stock solutions of the samples were prepared in DMF. Dilution series using sterile distilled water were prepared from 75 mg/ml to 1.0 mg/ml in microtest tubes and were transferred to 96 well micro titer plates. Bacterial and fungal suspensions that were grown overnight in double strength Mueller-Hinton broth were standardized to 10 CFU/ml using McFarland no. 0.5 standard solution. 100 μL of each organism suspension was then added into wells. The last well chain without any microorganisms was used as negative control. Sterile distilled water and the medium served as positive growth control. After incubation at 37 °C for 18–24 h, the first well without turbidity, was determined as the minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC). Chloramphenicol was used as standard antibacterial and ketoconazole as antifungal agent. The observed data on the antimicrobial activity of the compounds and control drugs are given in Table 2.

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